

FABRICATION OF METAL-MATRIX-PARTICULATE COMPOSITES
USING POWDER METALLURGY TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

It is advantageous to fabricate metal-matrix-particulate composites (MMPCs) using powder metallurgy (PM) because the fabricated composites possess a higher dislocation density, a small sub-grain size and limited segregation of particles, which, when combined, result in superior mechanical properties.

This paper reviews the various PM-related processes used currently in the fabrication of MMPCs, outlining the common problems encountered in each of these fabrication processes. The more recently developed PM techniques to fabricate MMPCs are also discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal-Matrix-Particulate Composites (MMPCs) as a group of advanced materials have been developed over the last twenty years[1-2]. Many methods have been developed to produce different metal-based composites[3-8]. Successful industrial applications have been reported and a series of MMPCs fabricated using the various methods are now commercially available[1,9-10].

Properties of MMPCs depend mainly upon the microstructure and properties of the matrix materials, the nature of particles, the distribution, size and shape of particles, and the interfacial behaviour between particles and matrix. Unfortunately, most particles employed to yield MMPCs possess poor wettability with the matrix metals, resulting in a poor distribution of reinforced particles and de-bonding at the particle-matrix interface. In order to enhance wettability, some "luxurious" techniques, such as surface coating by nickel, copper or titanium, have been introduced to preprocess the particles before fabrication. This preprocessing of particles raised the cost of MMPCs further, limiting a wider commercial applications of these MMPCs.

Some recently introduced MMPCs, using modern high-performance

materials like tungsten, molybdenum, niobium and tantalum as the metal matrix, are difficult to be fabricated by the conventional liquid metallurgy process due to the high temperatures involved [10-11]. In these cases, powder metallurgy (PM) with the near-net-shape capability is more attractive and it has become the most important fabrication technique for this group of MMPCs. The PM route also reduces the forming and machining cost correspondingly[10]. Furthermore, MMPCs with a high dislocation density, a small sub-grain size and limited recrystallization can be fabricated, resulting in superior mechanical properties[5, 9-12]. Another advantage of the PM processing is the easy attainment of a uniform distribution of particles in the metal matrix compared to other fabrication techniques since the segregation of particles is a common problem found in cast MMPCs[3-4].

2. FABRICATION OF GREEN COMPACTS OF MMPCS

2.1 Blending and Mixing

The blending or mixing, is just as important since it controls the final distribution of reinforcement particle and porosity in green compacts after compaction, which strongly affects the mechanical properties of PM materials produced. Segregation and clustering is a common problem associated with the present state-of-the-art blending or mixing methods. The phenomenon of segregation is inherent to any loose powder configuration which is subjected to mechanical blending[13-14]. The reason for segregation and clustering includes different flow characteristics between metal powders and reinforcement particles, and the tendency of the agglomeration of particles to minimize their surface energy[7].

As a general rule, a larger particle size will lead to a better degree of distribution. The shape of particles also influences the blending result: it is easier to mix metal powders with spherical particles than with irregular- or flake-like particles. The segregation behaviour of different size particles can be seen in Fig. 1 which shows the Monte Carlo Simulations of shaking a ternary system with equal area fractions of each species[13-14]. The larger particles rise up to the top as a result of the shaking because the larger particles are moved upward as smaller particles fill voids created beneath the larger particles. Segregation is complete after 290 cycles when the largest- and the intermediate-size particles are fully separated after all the smallest particles shifted to the bottom. Furthermore, the effect of different densities between particles and metal powders of similar size is significant during blending: the lighter particles tend to stay at the top, while the heavier particles primarily segregate to the bottom[5,7].

The segregation and clustering during blending can be overcome by a new technique developed during the 1960's called mechanical alloying (MA)[15]. Mechanical alloying is a dry, high-energy ball milling process for producing composite metal powders with a fine controlled microstructure[16-19]. A schematic representation of mechanical alloying is shown in Fig. 2[20-21]. This process consists of the repeated fracturing and rewelding of a mixture of particles and metal powders by high-energy compressive-impact forces to yield a uniform distribution of particles and metal powders with a satisfactory microstructure after compaction. In addition to the strengthening caused by uniformly dispersed fine particles, the fine grain size and the high dislocation density of the metal matrix, as a result of work

hardening of metal powders[15-21], also contribute to the strengthening of these MMPCs. Some processing details and properties of mechanical alloyed composites have been reported[17-19,22-25].

2.2 Compaction

Following the blending or mixing operation, the mixture is then pressed at room temperature in a die at pressures which make the powders adhere to each other to form a green compact with an appropriate density. This process is called cold compaction. In this process, the densities of the green compacts should be carefully controlled to ensure that the pores are well connected if outgassing process is to be employed later[5].

In the conventional method of compaction, a pressure is usually applied in one direction, resulting in an uneven distribution of consolidation, and sometimes, insufficient densities. This affects the subsequent processing of the green compacts such as sintering and secondary manufacturing. To better control the quality of green compacts, isostatic pressing techniques were developed such as cold, warm and hot isostatic pressing (C, W and HIP'ing)[26-27]. Cold isostatic pressing (CIP'ing) is mainly used to press powders under a high pressure. The advantages of CIP'ing over the other compaction methods include the uniformity of density of the compacts achievable regardless of the size and shape of powders; controllable shrinkage; and limited residual stresses resulting from the wall friction in one-dimensional pressing. Fabrication of green compacts using cold, warm or hot isostatic pressing techniques have been reported[5,6,8,26-29].

3. SINTERING AND OTHER CONSOLIDATION METHODS

3.1 Sintering of MMPCs

Usually, properly prepared green compacts are next sintered. The controllable parameters in this stage are the sintering temperature and sintering atmosphere. The commonly occurring problems are the presence of oxide films, the imperfect distribution of particles and sweating during liquid-phase sintering, and poor strength in solid-phase sintering[1,7]. The tendency for liquid metals to sweat out during sintering is due to the poor wettability of particles by liquid metal. An inadequate bonding between particles and metals at sintering temperature results in poor strength. To increase the wettability between particles and matrix has become one of the major concerns in the fabrication of MMPCs, especially for those composites that contain soft particles such as graphite[1,7,30].

3.2 Hot Pressing Methods

Sometimes, consolidation methods other than direct sintering are used. Hot isostatic pressing (HIP'ing) and vacuum hot pressing (VHP'ing) are the usual techniques employed here. Sargent et al.[31] have reported that for Al 6061-30wt% SiC_p composites, HIP'ing followed by extrusion resulted in a pronounced reduction in porosity and an increased strength (about 25% higher) as compared to the conventional route of extrusion.

A schematic representation of the VHP'ing process is given in Fig. 3[5]. Under a proper sintering temperature, gradual consolidation is accomplished by the maintenance of a constant pressure. The selection of the consolidation temperature is a compromise between the need to minimize the necessary pressure to produce optimum

density and degradation of the powder matrix. Zhou et al.[32] have tested Al 2024-15vol% SiC_p composites made by VHP'ing followed by hot extrusion and they found significant improvements in the mechanical properties of these composites.

3.3 High-Energy-High-Rate Processing

A recent progress in the consolidation of rapidly quenched powders containing a fine distribution of ceramic or graphite particles is known as high-energy-high-rate processing (HEHR)[33-37]. A schematic representation of the HEHR processing is shown in Fig. 4. Owen, Persad and co-workers[33-36] have reported that HEHR processes using a homopolar generator (HPG) is an attractive processing approach with the following desirable characteristics: 1) very fast processing to minimize time for internal oxidation, 2) rapid heating and cooling rates associated with the pulsed joule heating, 3) possible micro-encapsulation by preferential heating and local melting, and 4) a dense product with improved mechanical properties which can be achieved by simultaneous forging during discharge. Persad et al.[34] have concluded that in Al-SiC composites, the short-time-at-temperature approach offers the opportunity to control phase transformation and the degree of microstructural coarsening which is not possible using other powder processing methods. Many MMPCs have been produced using the HEHR processing; these include copper-graphite[33,35], aluminum-SiC[34], nickel-molybdenum-boride[36] and tungsten-based composites[35,37].

3.4 Resistance Sintering

Another sintering technique similar to the HEHR process is resistance sintering. This technique has been used to sinter fibre reinforced[38] or SiC_p-reinforced[39] aluminum alloys. In this process, a low-voltage, high-ampereage current is applied through the powder compact in a stainless steel die in which the compact is being compressed simultaneously. Instead of a homopolar generator, a welding machine with a capacity of 45 to 65 kVA is employed as the power source[38-39]. Almost full densification can be achieved under a proper pressure during resistance sintering. Since the sintering process is so fast (less than 1 second), no controlled atmosphere or vacuum is needed. The mechanical properties of such composites are excellent. Compressive yield stress of 500 to 700 MPa and compressive ultimate strength of 600 to 800 MPa can be reached for Al-30vol% SiC_p composites[39].

4. UNCONVENTIONAL PM PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

One of the unconventional techniques (Spray Deposition) is to co-spray liquid metal and dispersoid powders through an atomizer on a substrate to form billet, disk, strip or laminated structures[40]. Another is known as powder forging, which allows the direct forming of a mixture of metal powders and particles into a near-net-shape product[41]. Other methods include rapid solidification/ powder metallurgy[42] and different extrusion methods.

5. SUMMARY AND PROSPECTIVE

Fabrication processes of metal-matrix-particulate composites using powder metallurgy can be divided into three major operations: blending or mixing, compaction, and sintering and other consolidation methods. The current knowledge and common problems in each of the above operations have been reviewed separately. New developments in

fabrication techniques made in recent years have been enumerated and discussed in detail. These new techniques include mechanical alloying, cold, warm and hot isostatic pressing, vacuum hot pressing, resistance sintering and high energy high rate processing. A comparison of mechanical properties of Al-SiC_p composites fabricated using some of the methods discussed in the earlier sections is shown in the Table ; the mechanical properties of MMPCs fabricated by these techniques are clearly higher (especially the tensile strength and stiffness) than those produced using conventional PM methods. These newly developed techniques have greatly expanded the potential applications of PM in the fabrication of MMPCs.

The current limitations to a wider industrial applications of MMPCs are still the inadequate toughness and high cost of these materials. The low ductility and fracture toughness of MMPCs are mostly caused by the premature failure of the interfacial bonds, as a result of poor wetting and interfacial reactions between metal powders and reinforcement particles. These problems are expected to be solved by improvements in the low-temperature and high-pressure processes. Some new techniques developed to fabricate high-performance MMPCs have so far increased the cost of these final products because of the inclusion of expensive equipment and operations such as complex blending process, powder handling and consolidation. One of the most important directions for future research into the fabrication of PM MMPCs is therefore to develop ways to lower the processing cost without compromising the mechanical properties. This barrier is expected to be overcome in the not-too-distant future.

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Table The room-temperature mechanical properties of various Al-SiC_p composites fabricated using different PM methods

Matrix	Particle	Content (vol.%)	E (GPa)	UTS (MPa)	YS (MPa)	El. (%)
6013 (PM)*	SiC	15	101	517	434	6.3
6013 (PM)*	SiC	20	110	538	448	5.6
6061 (SD)=	SiC	11.5	79.3	330	293	8.2
6061 (SD)-	SiC	14	-	330	294	9.0
6061 (SD)-	SiC	28	-	362	322	5.0
6061 (PM)+	SiC	20	97	498	415	6.0
6061 (PM)<	-	-	70	290	255	17
6061 (PM)#	SiC	40	-	540	486	0.6
6061 (PM)\$	SiC	30	110	490	440	1
6061 (PM)&	SiC	30	119	417	397	-
6061 (PM)-	SiC	30	109	328	300	-
MB78 (PM)	-	-	-	380	452	11.9
MB78 (PM)#	SiC	20	-	560	500	1.8
MB78 (PM)	SiC	15	100	460	405	3.2
IN-9025 (PM)@	SiC	15	84	506	450	-
2124 (PM)z	-	-	74	442	277	29
2124 (PM)z	SiC	15	99	559	431	14
2124 (PM)!	SiC	15	106	570	412	7
2xxx (PM)x	SiC	15	103	524	372	7.5
2024 (PF):	SiC	20	105	510	410	-

Note: Some data were taken from average values.

E: Young's Modulus; UTS: Ultimate Tensile Strength; YS: Yield Strength; El: Elongation

* VHP+EXT[10]; = SD+Hot EXT[40]; + PM+EXT, < EXT[42]; \$ DWA Composites (PM)[43]; & HIP+EXT, - EXT[31]; # PM [40]; | ALCOA Composites (CIP+VHP+EXT)[43]; @ NOVAMET Composites (MA+PM)[18]; z VHP+Hot EXT[32]; ! PM+EXT[42]; x ALCOA Composites (PM)[8]; : Powder Forging[41].

(VHP: Vacuum Hot Pressing, EXT: Extrusion, SD: Spray Deposition, HIP: Hot Isostatic Pressing, PM: Powder Metallurgy, CIP: Cold Isostatic Pressing, PF: Powder Forging, MA: Mechanical Alloying)

Figure 1. Configurations at 0, 60, and 290 cycles from Monte Carlo simulations of the shaking of a ternary mixture of particles: The shaking amplitude is equal to the diameter of smallest particles. After[20-21].

Figure 2. A schematic representation of the repeated fragmentation and coalescence processes characteristic of mechanical alloying. The wordings suggest the various events that can be imagined to occur as they depend on the impact angle. After [13].

Figure 4. A schematic representation of the die assembly used in HEHR processing. After [33].

Figure 3. A schematic representation of the vacuum hot pressing. After [5].